

Rac-1a

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-82-s-RAC-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	9	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	XT 2 80 S RAC
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	10.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	8/2/2021 8:37:12 PM CST		
Date Processed:	8/2/2021 8:46:21 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	5.259	3230167	49.96	536377
2	6.167	3235025	50.04	457562

Asy-1a

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-82-s-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	08022
Vial:	120	Acq. Method Set:	20% quanbo
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	XT 2 82 S
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	7.2 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	8/2/2021 8:51:41 PM CST		
Date Processed:	8/2/2021 8:59:31 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	5.257	60022	1.12	10240
2	6.158	5282157	98.88	743161